

Technical Note

A simple method to prepare substrate-coated model particles for *in situ* enrichment of macromolecule-degrading microorganisms

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Abstract

Large biopolymers such as cellulose, chitin, and proteins constitute a major fraction of particulate organic matter (POM) in soils, sediments, and aquatic systems. Yet their microbial degradation remains difficult to study due to substrate heterogeneity, spatial complexity, and challenges in particle recovery. Here, we present a simple, low-cost, and versatile method to produce millimeter-scale substrate-coated model particles using gellan gum as a stable and biologically inert matrix. Insoluble polymer substrates (e.g. chitin or cellulose) are applied as surface layers or embedded within the gellan matrix, yielding particles that mimic physical and ecological properties of natural POM. The particles can be produced with minimal equipment, tailored in size and composition, and optionally rendered magnetic to facilitate gentle recovery from complex environments such as soils and sediments. When deployed in nylon mesh pouches, the particles permit unrestricted exchange of microorganisms, porewater, and metabolites with surrounding environments while enabling reliable retrieval after incubation. The approach is compatible with a wide range of downstream analyses, including microscopy, flow cytometry, amplicon sequencing, metagenomics, and cultivation-based assays. Such substrate-coated gellan-gum model particles provide a robust platform for investigating microbial colonization, functional succession, and macromolecule degradation across diverse environmental settings.

Introduction

Large biopolymers such as cellulose, chitin, and proteins constitute a major fraction of particulate organic matter (POM) entering soils and aquatic sediments. These macromolecules are central to carbon and nitrogen cycling, as their microbial degradation releases inorganic nutrients and smaller organic molecules that fuel further microbial activity. Understanding how these polymers are broken down is therefore critical for predicting organic matter turnover, nutrient availability, and the stability of soil

and sedimentary carbon pools. Yet, the decomposition of POM is highly complex, involving heterogeneous substrates, diverse microbial consortia, and tightly coupled enzymatic processes that are difficult to study *in situ*.

To address this complexity, researchers increasingly employ model particles that bait and select for specific biopolymer-degrading microorganisms and that can be recovered after incubation. They provide an experimentally tractable system that simplifies the natural complexity of POM. By following microbial colonization, enzymatic activity, and community succession, defined model particles better link substrate properties to microbial function and interaction dynamics. Microbial interactions on defined polymer particles drive rapid, substrate-specific microscale successions structured by competition and cross-feeding (Datta et al., 2016; Enke et al., 2018). Depth-resolved deployments of chitin particles further demonstrated that environmental gradients strongly shape particle-associated communities and metabolic strategies in the open ocean (Roberts et al., 2024). Using magnetic beads coated with either alginate or pectin, Bunse et al. (2016) revealed niche specialization within microbial communities colonizing these substrates during *in vitro* incubations of seawater. Only one study performed *in situ* incubations of substrate-coated magnetic and agarose beads deployed in the sulfidic Black Sea water column, showing rapid, substrate-specific colonization (Suominen et al., 2021). Model sulfur particles buried *in situ* revealed sulfur-cycling guilds in marine sediments (Pjevac et al., 2014). These studies collectively highlight that defined model particles are useful tools for identifying taxa actively degrading or transforming specific substrates without need of cumbersome stable isotope probing or enrichment cultivation.

Despite these advances, the broader application of particle-based approaches particularly in soils and sediments has been limited by practical constraints. Many existing particle systems depend on commercial matrices, complex surface functionalization, or substrates that are soluble or chemically unstable. However, these particles are often poorly suited for *in situ* applications in soils, sediments, and water columns because their micrometer-scale size leads to rapid dispersion, migration with pore water, and unreliable retrieval from complex matrices. In some applications, microbeads were confined within fine-mesh pouches, which may be suitable for bacterioplanktonic samples (Suominen et al., 2021) but restrict direct contact with solid phases and particle-associated microorganisms, limiting their applicability in heterogeneous environments.

Here, we present a low-cost, and easily adaptable method for generating model particles using low-acyl gellan gum as a stable structural matrix. By mixing and coating gellan gum with insoluble biopolymers, we create millimeter-scale particles that mimic

natural POM in soils and sediments, support selective colonization by macromolecule-degrading microorganisms, and can be deployed in sediments, soils, water columns, wastewater sludge, and stool. Gellan gum is used as the structural matrix because it is chemically and biologically relatively inert and provides a stable, transparent scaffold that resists rapid enzymatic degradation, although cases for microbial degradation have been reported. In contrast to agar, which is widely utilized as a carbon source by many microorganisms, particularly marine bacteria, gellan gum is far less commonly metabolized, thereby minimizing unintended background growth and ensuring that microbial colonization is primarily driven by the added target substrates rather than the scaffold material itself. Gellan gum is widely used as a gelling agent and replaces agar in the cultivation of, for example, thermophilic microorganisms. It contains fewer contaminating substances than agar and provides higher transparency. It has advantageous physicochemical properties such as high thermal stability, ion-mediated and tunable gel strength at low polymer concentrations, and resistance to microbial degradation (Das et al., 2015, Jaeger et al., 2015). Our approach supports common microbiological downstream analyses such as microscopy, amplicon sequencing, and metagenomics, making it a cost effective tool for studying the assembly, function, and temporal dynamics of particle-associated microbial communities.

Method description

Materials

- Gelrite™ gellan gum (Carl Roth)
- Chitin powder (shrimp shell-derived; Sigma-Aldrich) and microcrystalline cellulose powder (Sigma-Aldrich)
- CaCl₂
- Optionally: Fe₃O₄ (magnetite) powder (Sigma-Aldrich), neodymium magnet
- Milli-Q water
- Paper towels
- Petri dishes (10 cm diameter)
- 1 mL sterile pipette tips and sterile scissors
- Magnetic stirrer and heating plate
- UV sterilization source e.g. UV-PCR workstation
- 10 % + 70% ethanol
- Nylon mesh net < 3 mm mesh size

Step-by-Step Procedure

1. **Prepare gellan-gum solution**

Dissolve 0.8–1.5 g gellan gum in 100 mL distilled water under continuous stirring on a heated magnetic stirrer until fully solubilized. Autoclave the solution and keep liquified at 80 °C until use.

2. **Add cross-linker**

Add 1 mL of 800 mM CaCl₂ to the hot gellan-gum solution while stirring to promote stable gel formation.

3. **Add magnetite (optional)**

Remove the beaker from the magnetic stirrer and add 0.5–1% (w/v) nanocrystalline magnetite powder. Mix thoroughly to obtain a homogeneous suspension and keep the mixture at 80 °C until pouring. Magnetite should only be added after removal from the magnetic stirrer to avoid clumping of the dispersed particles.

4. **Prepare Petri dishes**

Line the bottom of each Petri dish with sterile paper towels and soak with 2 mL of a 3 mM NaCl or 800 mM CaCl₂ solution to favor rapid surface gelation. Remove excess liquid.

5. **Apply bottom substrate layer**

Evenly sprinkle 0.5-1 g of insoluble polymer substrate (e.g. chitin or cellulose powder) onto the soaked paper towel using a fine-mesh sieve, forming the bottom substrate layer.

6. **Pour gellan-gum solution**

Carefully pour >20 mL of the molten gellan-gum solution into each prepared Petri dish, pouring slowly and close to the surface to minimize resuspension or displacement of the bottom substrate layer.

7. **Apply top substrate layer**

When gelation becomes visible but is not yet complete, again evenly sprinkle an additional 0.5-1 g of the same insoluble polymer substrate onto the gel surface using a fine-mesh sieve to create a substrate-rich surface layer. Allow the gel to solidify completely at room temperature or °4C.

8. **Punch model particles with a cut-off pipette tip (Fig. 1a-c)**

Using sterile 1 mL pipette tips with the end cut off (opening ~3–4 mm), punch cylindrical particles from the solidified gel. Particles typically measure ~3–5 mm in diameter and height (Fig. 1c). Extrude the particles by firmly tapping the inverted pipette tip onto the bottom of a fresh Petri dish or sterile container, then transfer them to sterile water and gently wash to remove unbound substrate particles.

9. **Sterilize and store**

Sterilize the particles either by UV exposure (e.g. 2x 30 min in a UV-PCR hood)

or by brief and gentle washing in 70% ethanol for 1-2 min. Store particles in sterile distilled water at 4 °C or in high-saline NaCl solutions. If needed, extensively rinse particles with water and equilibrate with minimal mineral medium or ambient environmental water (e.g. filtered sea water).

Alternative preparation with polymer mixed into the gellan matrix

As an alternative to, or in combination with, the layered preparation, insoluble polymers (e.g. 2 g chitin or cellulose powder) can be directly mixed into the molten gellan solution prior to pouring. The suspension should be homogenized thoroughly to promote even distribution of the polymer within the gel matrix. However, because insoluble polymers sediment rapidly during gelation, this approach often results in preferential accumulation of substrate near the bottom of the Petri dish and potentially limited accessibility for microbes. The layered substrate application described above is therefore recommended when high substrate exposure at particle surfaces is desired.

***In situ* deployment of model particles**

For *in situ* incubations, mesh pouches were used to facilitate deployment and retrieval of model particles (Fig. 1g, Fig. 1h). Mesh pouches contained either substrate-coated gellan particles (e.g. chitin- or cellulose-coated) or substrate-free gellan particles, which served as negative controls. Pouches were made from nylon mesh with a mesh size <3 mm and secured with plastic clips. The mesh size still retains the model particles but also allows direct contact with the surrounding sediment, soil, or stool particles, permitting unrestricted exchange of microorganisms, porewater, and dissolved metabolites. Mesh pouches containing model particles can be embedded directly into the sediments or soils and incubated *in situ* for defined time periods. After retrieval, magnetic model particles can be separated from non-magnetic model particles (Fig. 1i) and further processed by cutting-off substrate-colonized and excluding non-target areas. Specifically, the outer layers enriched with polymer substrate (e.g., chitin or cellulose) can be precisely excised using a sterile scalpel, discarding the inner core of the cylinder where minimal substrate exposure and nonspecific colonization may occur. This selective sectioning enhances the specificity of downstream analyses (e.g., microscopy, flow cytometry, or metagenomics) by focusing on particle surfaces most representative of natural polymer-microbe interactions, thereby reducing background noise from gellan-only regions.

Figures

Figure 1. Preparation, handling, and deployment of substrate-coated gellan-gum model particles. (a) Solidified Gellan gum with chitin bottom and top layers after punching of model particles with a cut-off pipet tip (b) Model particles punched from the solidified gel in a cut-off sterile 1 mL pipet tip; layered chitin

zones are visible as opaque bands (c) Representative individual chitin model particles with typical dimensions ~3-5 mm in diameter and height (d-f) Stereomicroscope images of cylindrical gellan-gum model particle. (d) Chitin model particle (e) Cellulose model particle with neodymium magnetite added for recovery in front of white background (f) cellulose model particles with magnetite added for recovery in front of a black background

(g) Nylon mesh pouch mounted between two plastic clips used for in situ deployment and retrieval of model particles (h) Mesh pouch loaded with multiple substrate-coated particles prior to incubation; the coarse mesh (< 3 mm) allows unrestricted exchange with surrounding sediments, soils, or fecal material while retaining the particles. (i) Separation and recovery of magnetic cellulose model particles from non-magnetic chitin particles. All model particles were suspended in water and only magnetic cellulose model particles accumulated around a magnet placed beneath a sterile Petri dish. The embedded magnetite enables rapid magnetic separation and recovery from liquids or environmental matrices during washing and processing steps. The magnet-assisted retrieval facilitates gentle handling of particles while minimizing loss and disturbance of particle-associated microbial communities.

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